

Article Title: *Shoulder joint angles in supine and upright imaging of the pre-operative reverse total shoulder arthroplasty patient*

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<https://medicine.utah.edu/orthopaedics/research/labs/harold-dunn/groups/henninger>

This code analyzes scapulothoracic and glenohumeral joint angles from subjects pre-operative to reverse total shoulder arthroplasty (rTSA) using anatomic landmark data from supine CT scans and upright seated biplane fluoroscopy/optical motion capture. Anatomical coordinate systems for the torso, scapula, and humerus are defined based on landmark positions, guided by ISB recommendations (<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/15844264/>) but with variances to generate consistent analyses unaffected by posture and limitations of clinical medical imaging. Notably, the sternum is used as the definitive thorax Y-axis as it should be self-consistent between both supine and upright data collections.

The data is formatted in the same manner as prior releases of data from:

- healthy shoulders (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14889478>)
- shoulders after rTSA (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16537557>)

Of note, supine and upright data herein arose from some of the same subjects presented in the prior repository of rTSA subjects (e.g., Reverse_012, _013, _015, _016, _017, _018, and _019). The present study used static resting neutral data from the pre-operative visit (i.e., 00wk) which was not available in the prior release (but is included herein). A full release of pre-operative kinematics for 00wk is planned for later in 2025 and will be versioned in the prior rTSA repository.

Data contained in the present repository provide only deidentified anatomic landmarks (in Cartesian coordinates). Source DICOMs and 3D bone surface models may be available upon request.

File naming convention

Group_subject ID#_sex_age_side_activity_trial#_data

- i. E.g., Reverse_002_F_64_R_static_t01_output.xlsx – a subject with **Reverse** total shoulder arthroplasty, subject **#2**, that is **Female**, **64** years old, **Right** side imaged, in the static resting neutral pose, during **trial #1**, and this file contains all **data** relevant to the subject and activity
- ii. Static poses were captured in a resting neutral pose while seated upright, with elbows flexed 90 degrees, hands forward, thumbs up
- iii. Note: Subjects have the additional qualifier “_00wk”. These subjects were part of a study that collected both pre- (00wk) and post-op (e.g., 52wk) timepoints.

Provided Data Files

CT Landmarks.xlsx	<p>A spreadsheet containing the supine anatomical landmarks as measured from 3D reconstructions of the bones in CT. Herein the necessary landmarks included:</p> <p>Torso</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- SN – sternal notch- XP – xyphoid process (or distal sternal bisector [SB] if XP not visible)- C7 – process of the C7 vertebra <p>Scapula</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- TS – trigonum spinae- IA – distal tip of the inferior angle- GSC – post-operative glenosphere center (could substitute the glenoid center if this is available in otherwise healthy scapulae) <p>Humerus</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- LT – lesser tuberosity of the humerus- SCT – shaft cylinder, top- SCB – shaft cylinder, bottom
*_output.xlsx	<p>Spreadsheet containing the anatomical landmarks as measured from markerless tracking of biplane fluoroscopy/dynamic stereoradiography data. These sheets follow the format of prior repositories on Zenodo.org, with sheets for demographics (sheet1), scapular landmarks (scapula), humeral landmarks (humerus), and marker-based optical tracking of anatomic landmarks (vicon).</p>

Provided MATLAB Files (requires MATLAB R2021a or later)

a1_CreateTorsoCS.m	Script to transform raw data into the torso coordinate systems (runs on individual subject data)
a2_CreateScapCS.m	Script to transform data within torso coordinate systems to the scapula coordinate systems (runs on individual subject data)
a3_ST_joint_angles.m	Script to calculate scapulothoracic joint angles from data within the torso coordinate systems (runs as a batch on all subjects in the folder)
a4_GH_joint_angles.m	Script to calculate glenohumeral joint angles from data within the scapula coordinate systems (runs as a batch on all subjects in the folder)
a5_sternumanalysis.m	Script to calculate the synthetic xiphoid process (XP) axis from sternal bisector (SB) in supine CT (create and reformat data into the file "CT Landmarks – Corrected XP.xlsx").
a6_CTAnalysis.m	Script to compare supine and upright joint angles (includes all relevant calculations of supine joint angles from CT within – steps a3 and a4 do the same for the upright joint angles).
torso_cs.m	Function that creates torso coordinate system for upright data
torso_cs_ct.m	Function that creates torso coordinate system for supine data. The only difference to torso_cs.m is that there is no looping of the calculation.

scapula_cs.m	Function that creates scapula coordinate system for upright data
scapula_cs_ct.m	Function that creates scapula coordinate system for supine data. The only difference to scapula_cs.m is that there is no looping of the calculation.
humerus_cs.m	Function that creates humerus coordinate system for upright data
humerus_cs_ct.m	Function that creates humerus coordinate system for supine data. The only difference to humerus_cs.m is that there is no looping of the calculation.

Folders used by the code

Upright input files/00wk/	Contains input files of anatomic landmarks from subjects in the upright seated resting neutral posture at the pre-operative (00wk) timepoint
Torso CS Points/00wk/	Contains files of anatomic landmarks recast into the torso CS at the pre-operative (00wk) timepoint
Scap CS Points/00wk/	Contains files of anatomic landmarks recast into the scapula CS at the pre-operative (00wk) timepoint
Joint Angles/00wk/	Contains files of scapulothoracic (ST) and glenohumeral (GH) joint angles created using the YXZ and XZY Cardan sequences, respectively at the pre-operative (00wk) timepoint

Instructions

1. Run a1_CreateTorsoCS.m
2. Run a2_CreateScapCS.m
3. Run a3_ST_joint_angles.m
4. Run a4_GH_joint_angles.m
5. Run a5_sternumanalysis.m
6. Run a6_CTanalysis.m

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Refer to the following publications for detailed methods of data collection and prior analyses using data from this repository in studies performed by our team:

1. Kolz CW, Sulkar HJ, Aliaj K, Tashjian RZ, Chalmers PN, Qiu Y, Zhang Y, Foreman KB, Anderson AE, Henninger HB. Reliable interpretation of scapular kinematics depends on coordinate system definition. *Gait Posture*. 2020 Sep;81:183-190. doi: 10.1016/j.gaitpost.2020.07.020. Epub 2020 Jul 25. PMID: 32758918; PMCID: PMC7484087.
2. Kolz CW, Sulkar HJ, Aliaj K, Tashjian RZ, Chalmers PN, Qiu Y, Zhang Y, Bo Foreman K, Anderson AE, Henninger HB. Age-related differences in humerothoracic, scapulothoracic, and glenohumeral kinematics during elevation and rotation motions. *J Biomech*. 2021 Mar 5;117:110266. doi: 10.1016/j.jbiomech.2021.110266. Epub 2021 Jan 23. PMID: 33517243; PMCID: PMC7924070.

3. Aliaj K, Foreman KB, Chalmers PN, Henninger HB. Beyond Euler/Cardan analysis: True glenohumeral axial rotation during arm elevation and rotation. *Gait Posture*. 2021 Jul;88:28-36. doi: 10.1016/j.gaitpost.2021.05.004. Epub 2021 May 8. PMID: 33989999; PMCID: PMC8316370.
4. Aliaj K, Henninger HB. Kinematics-vis: A Visualization Tool for the Mathematics of Human Motion. *J Open Source Softw*. 2021;6(68):3490. doi: 10.21105/joss.03490. Epub 2021 Dec 21. PMID: 35079685; PMCID: PMC8786220.
5. Sulkar HJ, Zitnay JL, Aliaj K, Henninger HB. Proximal humeral coordinate systems can predict humerothoracic and glenohumeral kinematics of a full bone system. *Gait Posture*. 2021 Oct;90:380-387. doi: 10.1016/j.gaitpost.2021.09.180. Epub 2021 Sep 20. PMID: 34564010; PMCID: PMC8585709.
6. Aliaj K, Lawrence RL, Bo Foreman K, Chalmers PN, Henninger HB. Kinematic coupling of the glenohumeral and scapulothoracic joints generates humeral axial rotation. *J Biomech*. 2022 May;136:111059. doi: 10.1016/j.jbiomech.2022.111059. Epub 2022 Mar 24. PMID: 35367838; PMCID: PMC9081276.
7. Knighton TW, Chalmers PN, Sulkar HJ, Aliaj K, Tashjian RZ, Henninger HB. Anatomic total shoulder glenoid component inclination affects glenohumeral kinetics during abduction: a cadaveric study. *J Shoulder Elbow Surg*. 2022 Oct;31(10):2023-2033. doi: 10.1016/j.jse.2022.03.028. Epub 2022 May 10. PMID: 35550434; PMCID: PMC9481675.
8. Knighton TW, Chalmers PN, Sulkar HJ, Aliaj K, Tashjian RZ, Henninger HB. Reverse total shoulder glenoid component inclination affects glenohumeral kinetics during abduction: a cadaveric study. *J Shoulder Elbow Surg*. 2022 Dec;31(12):2647-2656. doi: 10.1016/j.jse.2022.06.016. Epub 2022 Aug 2. PMID: 35931329; PMCID: PMC9669184.
9. Sulkar HJ, Knighton TW, Amofo L, Aliaj K, Kolz CW, Zhang Y, Hermans T, Henninger HB. In Vitro Simulation of Shoulder Motion Driven by Three-Dimensional Scapular and Humeral Kinematics. *J Biomech Eng*. 2022 May 1;144(5):051008. doi: 10.1115/1.4053099. PMID: 34817051; PMCID: PMC8822462.
10. Sulkar HJ, Aliaj K, Tashjian RZ, Chalmers PN, Foreman KB, Henninger HB. Reverse Total Shoulder Arthroplasty Alters Humerothoracic, Scapulothoracic, and Glenohumeral Motion During Weighted Scaption. *Clin Orthop Relat Res*. 2022 Nov 1;480(11):2254-2265. doi: 10.1097/CORR.0000000000002321. Epub 2022 Jul 20. PMID: 35857295; PMCID: PMC9555951.
11. Sulkar HJ, Aliaj K, Tashjian RZ, Chalmers PN, Foreman KB, Henninger HB. High and low performers in internal rotation after reverse total shoulder arthroplasty: a biplane fluoroscopic study. *J Shoulder Elbow Surg*. 2023 Apr;32(4):e133-e144. doi: 10.1016/j.jse.2022.10.009. Epub 2022 Nov 5. PMID: 36343789; PMCID: PMC10023281.
12. Zitnay JL, Tashjian RZ, Walch G, Chalmers PN, Joyce CD, Henninger HB. Inlay vs. onlay humeral components in reverse total shoulder arthroplasty: a biorobotic shoulder simulator study. *J Shoulder Elbow Surg*. 2024 Jun;33(6):1377-1386. doi: 10.1016/j.jse.2023.10.015. Epub 2023 Nov 28. PMID: 38036254; PMCID: PMC11098709.
13. Zitnay JL, Stout MR, Percin B, Tashjian RZ, Chalmers PN, Joyce CD, Walch G, Henninger HB. Isolated humeral distalization in reverse total shoulder arthroplasty: a biorobotic shoulder simulator study. *J Shoulder Elbow Surg*. 2025 May;34(5):1280-1290. doi: 10.1016/j.jse.2024.07.055. Epub 2024 Oct 5. PMID: 39369948; PMCID: PMC11971388.